

The Poem “I Will Never Forget For The Poet Muhammed Al-Mahi A Linguistic Study

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 11, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August 25, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Al-Mahi, Morphology, Language</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5254777</p>	<p><i>This is a linguistic study to the poem of the Egyptian poet Muhammad Mustafa Al-Mahi. One of the classical poets from Damietta in Egypt died in 1967 and he one of the adheres to the classical poetry, and contemporary literary schools have not attracted him , so his poetry came with a strong formulation, gentle rhythm and clear meanings and he wrote about most of the poetry purposes. He passed away in 1976. He has a collection of three hundred twenty-seven pages in two editions and from this collection I chose a poem (I will never forget) which purpose is spinning, and he wrote it in fifteen verses with (Al-Tawil) meter, in these lines, I tried to study the poem a linguistic study so I studied at the phonemic level the repetition that was apparent in it, as for the morphological level, the sources, derivatives, and irregular plurals are selected, also, at the grammatical level, I studied the methods such as negation, interrogation, condition, exclusion, and appeal.</i></p>

Introduction

Praise be to Allah, Lord of the worlds, and by Him we seek assistance, and may blessings and peace be upon the best of all of his creation, and the Guide to the Day of Judgment, our Prophet and our intercessor Muhammad and his good and pure family, and his chosen companions.

It went to my mind to identify one of the classical poets from Egypt, the poet Muhammad Mustafa al-Mahi, born in 1967, and his collection (Al-Mahi poets).

I chose from this collection one of the wonderful sentimental poems, entitled (I will not forget). This poem is consisting of sixteen lines of (Al-Tawil) meter. I tried to read this poem a linguistic reading, so I extracted from it the linguistic features, such as phoneme, morphology and grammar, and in all this I referred to the connotations inspired by these features.

The study was divided into three sections: the phonemic level represented by the phenomenon of repetition, the morphological level, represented by the structures of derivatives, sources and plurals, and the grammatical level represented by the methods, such as negation, interrogation, condition, exception and appeal. Referring in all of this to every connotation that this reading came out to, and in all this I followed a descriptive and analytical approach.

Preface

Introducing the poet and his poetic output

The poet Muhammad Mustafa Al-Mahi was born in Damietta, Egypt in the year 1895, where he grew up and received his education in its schools, then he got a job in the Endowment office, so he excelled in his work with creativity, and was trusted by his superiors and everyone who contacted him, until he was appointed as a general superintendent in the ministry of Endowments until 1937, when the Egyptian government chose him - based on the wish of the Iraqi government - to be an expert in endowments affairs, to organize Iraqi endowments.

The poet made a good and commendable effort in his work, and prepared a full report that the government printed and deposited by its libraries to benefit from it. Therefore, King Ghazi granted him the High-Class Medal of Mesopotamia, and he was the first Egyptian to be awarded this award. Muhammad Mustafa Al-Mahi died in 1967. 1.

His poetic output:

The Al-Mahi poet considered one of the elders of poets in Egypt, and a contemporaneous one of the two great poets Ibrahim Nagy and Ali Mahmoud Taha Al-Muhandis.

Muhammad Mustafa Al-Mahi's poetry was characterized by stoicism and elegance in the phrase, with clarity in the meanings and beauty in the wording, as well as coherence and strength between the word and its meanings. We find in the poetry of Al-Mahi a creative energy, which we can see in the poems of his collection, as he combined the witty of topics with seriousness of ideas.

In his poetry, Al-Mahi also mixed between the old and the modern, so he keeps pace with the innovators in what they go to, while preserving and adhering to the existence of ancient Arabic poetry, so he did not try to diversify rhymes like the innovators did, but he was renewed with images, meanings and topics, saying, "I am not in this

opinion an enemy of renewal but I hate the boom, and I think that is the best thing to serve the Arab poetry is to bring it closer to others, and to be keen above all on the Arab approach, while diversifying its purposes, arts, imaginations and meanings, in line with time and the needs of the era in which we live, so that our writers with this only can boast of clear, modern Arabic poetry. That is what I came after and worked for it, and I hope that I have succeeded in it".²

And the poem "I will never forget" - the subject of study - is one of the sentimental poems in the collection where Al-Mahi constructs this poem with sweetest words that express with them his old love which still beats in his soul's corners in spite of the long time passed over it.

Al-Mahi resorted to the language of dialogue in presenting his pains and complaints from his age, similar to those reading the pendants in the Jahiliyyah, such as the commentator of a man of Omr'u Al-Qais when he interviewed his friends in his poem "Qafat Nabek" and Al-Mahi here as well talk to his friends once, and call them once again to tell him about his beloved and relieve him by mention his beloved who did not get, as he says:³

Let me shed tears significantly, so it is not me that the tears can be cured

Yes, and I remember that if Allah judged a separation between us, I will not forget the covenant

My friends - and hopes do not convince the brave - stand up, my heart has thrown me in confusion

Stand and tell me about my beloved for a while, that is something could relieve my illness

Stand and relieve me with whom was her memory is my joy the days make my home empty

Believe you both, passion is the beginning of the death, and that it has something that pleases the enemies

From gestures that bewitch the heart, to smiles that leave the heart suffering

You have a covenant if it remembered, it will return to us the freshness of life again

My best is to complain and it does not benefit me, will my complaints attract the eternity kindness

My friend, I will not forget - even if it was long time - a time that we were together and her speech to me - when she settled smoothly - I would sacrifice you, and if I find you one day will be and when we settled in a beautiful garden and you don't see but only flowers around

We stayed there and the weather was clear, like the hearts of the virgins filled with their wishes

My excuse that the world became serious, and events awakened those who were not

I knew about the calamities and its impact, so when they became around me, it did not terrify my heart

In this paper, I will try to read the poem "I will never forget" a linguistic reading, in which I point out all linguistic aspects, including phonemic, morphological, and grammatical levels.

Phonological study:

The first thing that catches the reader's attention is the phenomenon of repetition, which is one of the most important rhythmic phonemic phenomena in poetry, because it gives the poem a kind of internal music that the listener's ear can enjoy and harmonize with, on the condition that the poet realizes that even if repetition is easy, sometimes deceiving the poet and signing it in the expressive mistake, because it "has a deceptive nature, for even if it is easy and capable in creating music, it can mislead the poet and make him fall into an expressive mistake. It contains expressive possibilities that enrich the meaning if the poet can control him and employ him in its position, otherwise it turns into a mere trite repetition"⁴

Terms of repetition:

Repetition has conditions ancient and modern linguists have agreed upon them, and if these conditions are met for repetition in a text, it results in a coherent text, but to be that repetition has a high rate in the text, and it doesn't mean by high rate that repetition is too much, because the frequent repetition shows the linguistic poverty of the text writer, and therefore it is not acceptable due to its lack of coherence. "Repeating long phrases or complete syllables can be harmful because they frustrate the informing, unless there is strong motivation"⁵

Repetition should also help decipher the text and realize its semantic role in it. It is not merely a repetition of a word or a specific phrase, but rather the aim of it is to understand the text and confirm the information within it, therefore, the reference must be standardized, "the word repetition requires the standard reference according to the stability and limiting principles"⁶ that if the repeated element refer to a certain reference, and keep referring to the same reference in the text, then the text will be one cast and influential unit at the same time.

But if the referred reference differs, the recipient will be confused in searching for it, so we cannot find a textual cast.

Repeat function

Repetition with these conditions, becomes capable of coherence and casting the text, as it plays a fundamental role in this casting, and it contributes to tightening the text by successively in the repetition of the repeated elements, because the repetitive element gives a sign other than that which the first element gave, in addition to the significance of the emphasis that continuity adds to it by repeating the element.

Repetition also comes for the purpose of drawing attention to something the creator of the text wants, whether poetry or prose, and repetition shows the psychological and intellectual value expressed by the creator of the text, by emphasizing the repetition of a specific word or phrase.

Repetition also has a persuasive communicative role, as it is considered an important means of discussions, in addition to the aesthetic that it imparts to any molding text, so it's not hidden the tons provoked by the repetition inside the text.

And the reason for the writer's resort to repetition may be the listener, as it is possible that the listener is not alert, or has a lack of awareness, so the speaker resorts to the method of repetition to ensure that the information reaches the mind of the listener. There are types of repetition, which are the repetition of the letter, the repetition of the word and the repetition of the phrase, and what we found in the poem of Al-Mahi poem, of these types are two types:

First: The repetition of the letter, which is one of the "phonemic interference resulting from repeating a specific letter, or a number of letters that have tonal value that function symbiotically in the performance of the idea and emotion" 7

The repetition of a specific letter in the poem indicates the poet's psychological state and feelings, and by reviewing the poem, we find a repetition of the letter N, as he repeated it forty times, as N is one of the sounds that have auditory clarity and he repeated it in his verses that indicates his feelings of sadness and pain, cause the letter N is one of best Arabic phonemics in expressing sadness and pain.

He also repeated the letter H, which is a silent, frictional whispered letter 8, and by repeating this whispered letter, the poet expressed his hidden sorrows and groans as saying:

Stand up and tell me about my love for a while, because that reliefs my pain and sickness

Al-Mahi adopted the letter Y as a rhyme for his poem, which is one of the Alphabetical letters, so this letter shared with the rhythm of the poetic verses, and expressed the poet's emotions and feelings, as it a letter has a connotation to the poet's feelings and groans, where he repeated it 37 times which add a tonal bell on the poem that made it harmonized with the poet's feelings experience.

Second: Repetition of the word because it represents an acoustic feature and a major component of the rhythm. It deepens the meaning sought by the poet, so he repeated the act of "standing" three times, because he wanted to confirm his love as if he was begging his companions to talk to him about his love to bring out the pain in his heart, where he says:

My friends, the hops can not convince the man, stand up, my heart confused me

Stand up and tell me about my love for a while cause that relief my sickness

Stand up and relief me with the one who her mentioning is my companion if days make my house empty

Also, the poet Al-Mahi, repeated the word (forget) in a negation way by saying:

Yes, I remember, if Allah judge us with a separation, I will never forget our covenant

My friends, I will not forget our old times that we will relief our contact for the present time

He showed and confirmed that he did not forget the covenant that he repeated three times, to show the intensity of his keenness on that beloved covenant to his heart.

As for the morphological side, we find in this poem some structures of infinitives towards:

Action: This construction is the source of the necessary and transgressive triple the infinitive (FAaL): this infinitive came as source to the triple imperative and transgressive verb when the verb is weighted to (Faal Yafaa, Fel Yafal) because the verbs like this will be on three structures: (Faal Yafaal, Fal Yafaal, Fil Yafaal, so the infinitive will be (Falla))9

This source was mentioned in the words of al-Mahi:

My best is to complain, and it's does not benefit me, and will the time fall for my complaint?

So, he used the infinitive (fell), to indicate that his pain and complaints are great and many, and that this continuous complaint is fixed, as time does not and will not be answered, so he used the metaphorical question that came out to the meaning of despair from salvation.

(TAFEEL): This comes as a source for the triple verb, increased by doubling on the weight (Faal)10, from that the saying of Al-Mahi:

Stand up and tell me about my love for a while because that relieve my sickness

So, he used the source (relieving) of the verb (relieve), to describe the pain of his heart and that he suffers the pain of love, so he asks his friends to tell him about his beloved because that will relieves his love pain, so this infinitive came in this position to express the poet exaggerate in describing the love sickness.

(FILLAH): It is a source brought to refer to the occurrence of the event 11, and it is formulated from the abstract triple verb. Al-Mahi used this weight to indicate how the action took place, so he said:

From gestures that fascinate the heart, to smiles that leave the heart suffering

The infinitive (Fascinate) came from the verb (FATAN) , where the poet wanted to indicate the charm of the gestures of his beloved, and that she stole his heart when she turned, so he came with the source of the body to indicate this meaning.

The infinitives of irregular plurals:

Irregular plurals is "what refer to three or more (in Arabic), and has a singular that shares its meaning and its origins, with an inevitable change that occurs to its form when plural." 12

(AFAAL): This syntax is a plural of every triple noun that is not combined as verbs, as Al-Mahi saying:

Stand up and relief me with the one who her mentioning is my companion if days make my house empty
I excuse the days, it became serious, and events awakened those who were playing
So (days) and (events) came plural on the weight (AFAAL), which are the plural of day and event.

Derivative structures:

1- the participle: It is an adjective that is derived from the imperative verb to refer to the one from whom the verb occurred. 13

The participle was mentioned in the poem of Al-Mahi from the trio, and he made it a rhyme for his poem, as he say:

Let me shed tears, because it is not for me that I see the tears healer
Yes, I mention that if Allah judged us with a separation, then I will not forget the covenant

To his say:

From gestures that fascinate the heart, to smiles that leave the heart suffering
My friends, I will not forget our old times that we will relief our contact for the present time

I excuse the days, it became serious, and events awakened those who were playing
So, we find the participle in the words (Hamiya, Shafia, Nasia, Ania, Halia, Lahiya) to indicate the situation, as the poet sheds his tears as a liquid, despite his knowledge that the tears will not help and will not heal his heart and he still holding their covenant and did not forget his love to whom stolen his heart that suffered from nostalgia and solicitude, and this is how the participle came to indicates the poet's steadfastness on the one hand, and the renewal of this love on the other hand, but it was renewed that does not amount to the verb's sign of regeneration.

We also note the participle from the quadrable verb in the word ((معيد)) repeater) in the poet's saying:

What a covenant would you have if it would return to us the freshness of life again

From the quadruple verb (return اعاد), the poet has modified the verb by returning the participle a repeater to the verb repeat, for the evidential connotation in it. We also notice the exaggeration of the participle, in the word (knowledgeable) in the words of Al-Mahi:

I knew about the troubles and their impact, so when they came, my heart was not terrified

The term "knowledgeable علم" is based on the weight (Faeel فعيل), a form transmitted from syntaxis of the adjective, indicating by it "the suffering and repetition of the matter, until it became as if it was part of its owner and a nature of it." 14

3- The accusative noun: which refer to the event and the occurrence and the object 15 and is formulated from the triple on the weight (Mafool), and from the quadrable verb to the weight of its present and changing the present letter to M, and the accusative name was mentioned in Al-Mahi poem with the word (mvfmat) in his saying:

We stayed there and the weather was clear, as it was like the hearts of virgins full of hope

The accusative noun here refers to continuation¹⁶ as the hearts of the virgins are full of continuous, renewed wishes.

Grammatical study:

With a linguistic reading of a poem (I will never forget), we notice that Al-Mahi used some grammatical methods, with which he linked the meanings of the poem, so it came in a series of meanings with a series of images. These methods are:

1- Negation: It is a method of denial, which is used in the text to remove an order in the mind of the recipient, and the tools of negation that are mentioned in Al-Mahi poem are (no, what, why, not).

Al-Mahi said:

My friends, the hops cannot convince the man, stand up, my heart confused me

The tool (not) here is not working, because it entered the present tense verb (convince), as it is a negation of the event, and its connotation here is the news.

As for his saying:

My friends, I will not forget our old times that we will relief our contact for the present time

He used the tool (not) and did not use (no), so he did not say (no forget) even though both of them are for negation, because the meaning of (no) "is to inform the addressee of what he did not know or what is given this status, as for (not) it is a response on saying and correcting a suspicion "17 The poet wanted to inform the addressee that he had not forgotten his covenant with his beloved, and he would pay the suspicion or respond to the saying of those who suspect that he forgot that beautiful era and his saying:

I knew about the troubles and their impact, so when they came, my heart was not terrified

So the poet used "wasn't", which is a letter of negation, and it entered into the present tense verb (terrified) of the quadrable verb (terrify) which is stressed, so he denied terrorizing and intimidating his heart, and turning the time of the present tense to the past, meaning that it is not terrified now or in the past, and this is an indication of the hardness of his heart, and the extent to which he bears the troubles and his saying:

Let me shed tears, because it is not for me that I see the tears healer

Yes, I mention that if Allah judged us with a separation, then I will not forget the covenant

My best is to complain, and it's does not benefit me, and will the time fall for my complaint?

When we stayed at a garden with dew, and do not see but roses

We notice the repetition of the verb of negation (not), which is one of the past letters that refer to negation, and the poet used this verb extensively in his poem, to indicate the renewal of negation.

2- The Interrogation: It is a "linguistic method based on the request for understanding." 18 The interrogation method is mentioned in the poem (I will never forget) with the tool (Will) only, and it is an interrogation by which approval is requested without perception and does not enter into an exile or a condition, as the poet says:

My best is to complain, and it's does not benefit me, and will the time fall for my complaint?

So here (Is) departed from the real question, as the poet does not ask for an answer to his question, but rather wants to denounce." And it seems most likely that the meaning of the negation learned from (Is) does not match the negative with the letter of the negation ... Rather it is an interrogation with the meaning of the negation, it may be with Negation an exclamation or disapproval. "19

3- The condition: (that the thing happened due to the occurrence of others) 20 and has many tools like the tool (if), and it is a conditional tool that is often used in places that are likely to happen, or in places whose occurrence is suspected21, and Al-Mahi said:

Yes, I mention that if Allah judged us with a separation, then I will not forget the covenant

So the conditional (if) entered on the past tense (judge), which reported the reception 22 although it is a past verb, but it is expected to happen, so he did not say (if it was done) because if it is used in matters that are certain to happen, as for the answer, there is an incomplete past verb issued with (that) to confirm the answer, and confirm that he has not forgotten the covenant and his saying:

Stand up and relief me with the one who her mentioning is my companion if days make my house empty

The condition here came with the conditional (if), and its answer was preceded on the verb of the condition, and the answer to the condition was presented that (Basra linguists) did not permit. As for the Kufis, it is permissible to present the answer on the condition, whether the answer is past or present. But we prefer the Kufis opinion because it's fit to the Quran style and in the poem of Al-Mahi, the answer was proceeding the (her mention as my companion) to the condition (If the days make my house empty), as the origin of the speech is: Stopping the reasoning for me that if the days empty my house from her who was my companion.

4- The exception: It is the removal of what is after except from the ruling of what before it 26, and the exception was mentioned in Al-Mahi poem in his saying:

When we stayed at a garden with dew, and do not see but roses

Around me the flowers: the admirer is its flower (the collection), so the poet used the method of exclusion in this verse, so it indicates the restriction, and after that, there is a second verb for (see).

5- The call: It is the request of the come of the caller, and the call was mentioned in the poem of Al Mahi added to the speaker in his saying:

My friends, the hops cannot convince the man, stand up, my heart confused me

My friends, I will not forget our old times that we will relief our contact for the present time

The poet calls on his companions, and he pleads with them to be slow, because his heart has confused him, and assures them that he has not forgotten the time of connection with the beloved. We also find the call in the style of exclamation, where he said:

What a covenant for you, if its remembrance returns to us the freshness of life again

Conclusion:

1- Repetition had an effective role in highlighting the intended connotation, as it gave the poem a rhythmic dimension and a musical bell, through which the poet tried to send a clear meaning to the recipient. The repetition of Al-Mahi was not limited to the rhythmic aspect, but went beyond it to the semantic side. Therefore, its patterns varied in response to the poet's experience, represented by the repetition of the letter and the repetition of the word.

2- The morphological study highlighted the connotation of the poem, so the derivatives had semantic dimensions determined by the context, and the source of infinitives and the plurals had a prominent role in imparting the poet's sign of regret and remorse over his past time.

3- The grammatical methods also showed the poet's distress through the method of appeal, exception, interrogation, and other methods that were studied within the research pages.

Recommendations:

The collection of Muhammad Mustafa Al-Mahi's poet is considered one of the collections that isn't lucky to be studied and analysis, and I hope to whom read it to study it and analysis it because it worth for what it contains of metaphoric and technical touches.

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